

GIFTED CHILDREN: WHAT IS THEIR PLACE IN THE BRAZILIAN EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM?

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ABSTRACT

This essay addresses the topic of gifted children, questioning, in a forceful way, their place in the Brazilian educational system of teaching and learning. Its scientific relevance lies in the fact that this is a subject about which very little is said, with scientific and empirical depth and yet the published works deal superficially with the issue of pedagogical responsibility towards such individuals. Its social relevance is presented by the fact that a society only develops through the creativity of its citizens and, on the path that advances, by leaps and bounds, the Brazilian learning system will, in a short time, be a country without any scientific talents. . This is an essay, based on the pedagogical praxis of the authors and on productions that help in the fabric of the criticism presented. Addressing the issue of giftedness and high abilities in children is a

challenge for regular schools; This is proving to be a complete failure, for the simple reason that there is no strategic action plan, based on empirical studies, case studies, and qualified professionals to guide them through their respective cognitive challenges.

Keywords: Gifted children. Children with high abilities. Contemporary school curriculum. Regular School.

INTRODUCTION

Children with special talents, highly developed in certain areas of human knowledge, in such a way that they are completely outside the standard curve of normality is a phenomenon to which they have given the name giftedness and/or high abilities, because, as a rule, these individuals are very powerful in certain fields, which attracts the attention of their teachers and caregivers; however, they seek to ignore the cognitive areas in which they can be considered as within the global average.

What makes them stand out, in relation to the majority of their age category, is their keen ability to learn things that other children their age would not normally be able to learn, even though they have a great instructor and an entire teaching structure at their disposal. .

Here, it is worth highlighting that, although Howard Gardner will say that this is a type of Piagetian determinism and that learning is accessible to any child at any age and, in addition to this scientist, there are readers of Vygotsky (1896-1934) who, without knowing the details of the empirical meaning of *Zone of Proximal Development*, they will dare to say that it is enough for an adult or an older child to teach them something complex and they will pass on, namely, the content even before the mental age required for such learning.

It turns out that the gifted child and/or with high skills not only knows the empirical procedures of the action, but also knows how to explain its practical application, how to do it, why to do it and, when not to do it, in addition to reporting the behavior of the target object of your experience when subjected to pressure.

This ability, in particular, reveals that the child's thinking is already mature enough to the point of demonstrating conditions to be able to wander between the concrete and the abstract, allowing him to apply his intelligence on things and situations, manifesting it through of creativity.

It must be clarified that giftedness is revealed not only through the ability to demonstrate a single attribute, such as memory, *e.g.*, or ease in learning foreign languages, or the ability to calculate mathematical numbers, memorize formulas; is something much broader and more

complex, because it requires the individual to be able to abstract and weave deep connections with the contents they explore, expressing the reasons that lead to such situations and what motivates, enables or prevents them, producing, as a result of such empirical observations, plausible syntheses.

Instead of being an excellence and a condition worthy of admiration, it ends up more like an object that causes more pain and anguish in whoever presents it; because these children do not find a suitable place in society, based on the premise that their desires are different, much more complex and different from what would be and could be considered normal for a given chronological age. This is the first challenge, because their mental age is far beyond the reasonableness and normality considered by common sense and the castrating pedagogy that absolutely prevails in the Brazilian education system.

Following in the wake of this problem, a common sense ideology that wants everyone to be *equal*, no more and no less; and, therefore, when separating such children in order to allow them to have access to more advanced content than their peers, this is treated as elitism; for being more capable than others and, therefore, in the name of socialization, what they are left with is the common grave of equality, which serves as a euphemism to camouflage the exasperated collective ignorance.

Addressing the issue of giftedness and high abilities in children is a challenge for regular schools; This is proving to be a complete failure, for the simple reason that there is no strategic action plan, based on empirical studies, case studies, and qualified professionals to guide them through their respective cognitive challenges.

GIFTED CHILDREN

This represents a complex topic, because the limits that determine the high capabilities of a human being must be measured based on determinants, duly tested and proven by science and, in continuation of this reasoning, individuals potentially classified in this way must be evaluated with scientific rigor, through standardized tests and by professionals with recognized experience in such assessment methods.

In general lines,

Giftedness is characterized by the high potential of aptitudes, talents and abilities, evidenced in high performance in the student's various areas of activity and/or to be evidenced in the child's development. However, there must be consistency of such skills over time, in addition to a significant level of performance in the area of giftedness. In many cases, the PRECOCITY of

the appearance of SKILLS and the resistance of individuals to the obstacles and frustrations that exist in their development are recorded (BRASIL, 2006, p. 11). [Italics are in the original].

For Costa, Bianchi and Santos (2022), knowledge about the characteristics of these children contributes to understanding the phenomenon of giftedness and to the implementation of actions aimed at their specific needs. The main characteristics identified in children with high abilities/giftedness are: speed in learning; ease of abstraction, associations, analysis and synthesis, generalizations; taste for challenges and persistence and adaptability in the face of unexpected difficulties; prolonged concentration on activities of interest; boredom with routine; independence and autonomy; interest in different areas and topics; good memory; concentrated attention; high degree of curiosity; high oral and written comprehension skills; rich vocabulary and interest; and also, different interests and advanced vocabulary, which can make it difficult to relate to peers of the same age. These characteristics may vary according to each child, but in general, they present a high level of intelligence in one or more areas of interest.

According to Attoni *et al* (2020), children with high abilities/giftedness may present the following characteristics in relation to language: broad and sophisticated vocabulary; high oral and written comprehension skills; sensitivity to nuances of language, such as irony, sarcasm and ambiguity; more elaborate and sophisticated language; early interest in reading; more advanced expression skills; more developed argumentation and persuasion capacity. These characteristics can be used as indicators to identify children with high abilities/giftedness, considering that they may have a broader vocabulary and a greater capacity for expression. Furthermore, children with high abilities/giftedness may have difficulty relating to peers of the same age, due to their advanced vocabulary and different interests.

According to the understanding expressed by Attoni *et al* (2020), to stimulate the language of children with high abilities/giftedness, the following can be done: provide an environment rich in stimuli, with books, games, educational toys and activities that challenge child to think and express themselves in a creative and elaborate way; encourage reading from an early age, offering books appropriate to the child's age and level of development; encourage writing, whether through diaries, stories, poetry or other forms of written expression; offer activities that encourage argumentation and persuasion, such as debates, group discussions and presentations; provide challenges that stimulate creativity and problem solving, such as logic games and puzzles; value and encourage oral expression, offering opportunities for children to express themselves and share their ideas and opinions; offer constructive and encouraging feedback, valuing the child's creativity and originality; and also adapt the curriculum and school

activities to meet the child's needs and interests, offering challenges appropriate to their level of development.

In this sense, it is worth highlighting that each child is unique and may have different needs and interests. Therefore, it is essential that parents and educators are aware of the particularities and singularities presented and, based on understanding the cognitive manifestations, offer stimuli appropriate to their profile and expected level of development.

Attoni *et al* also state that children with high abilities/giftedness can show great ease in learning, with mastery and quick clarity over concepts, in addition to a more elaborate and sophisticated language. These authors highlight that language can be an extremely important tool for identifying children with high abilities/giftedness, since they can have a broader vocabulary and a greater capacity for expression.

Giftedness is a challenge to be understood, because society is not prepared to receive and live with such individuals. They hinder the conduct of pedagogical and didactic work in schools, which are prepared to serve the masses, offer training in quantity to the detriment of quality, and children who are above average demand a type of experience that satisfies their curiosity and his desire for knowledge, which in a very short time already takes on more elevated airs and, if what is proposed no longer challenges him, he disperses, going in search of something that proves more charming.

This particular characteristic leads to biased and erroneous diagnoses of Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) and the magic solution found by *experts* is to give a pill that keeps the child focused on the teacher's (pathetic) class, which follows a curriculum whose The objective is to promote equity among students and provide intellectual training. Any similarity with the *glass school*, described by Ruth Rocha, is purely coincidental.

Alencar and Fleith (2001, sp) highlight some characteristics common to gifted children:

Great curiosity about objects, situations or events, with involvement in many types of exploratory activities; self-initiative tendency to start activities alone, to pursue individual interests and to seek one's own direction; originality of oral and written expression, with constant production of different responses and non-stereotyped ideas; unusual talent for expression in arts, such as music, dance, theater, drawing and others; ability to present alternative solutions, with flexibility of thought; openness to reality, seeking to keep up with what surrounds you, sagacity and observation capacity; ability to enrich problem situations, select responses, search for solutions to difficult or complex problems; ability to use knowledge and information in the search for new associations, combining elements, ideas and experiences in a peculiar way; capacity for superior judgment and evaluation, consideration and search for logical answers, perception of implications and consequences, ease of decision-making; production of varied ideas and responses, a taste for improving the solutions found; taste for taking risks in various activities;

ability to see relationships between seemingly unrelated facts, information or concepts; and, fast, easy and efficient learning, especially in the field of your skill and interest.

These conditions presented are of a generic nature and can occur in different areas, highlighting that, in some cases, many of these characteristics may be absent. With this, it is highlighted that, according to the school models and learning curriculum that contemporary society has, a student who presented himself in these conditions would be condemned to psychotropic poisoning, in the name of *socialization* and *equality* .

On the other hand, among the behavioral characteristics of students with high abilities/giftedness, it can also be noted, in some cases, according to experts from the MEC Special Education Secretariat:

Need for own definition; ability to develop specific interests or skills; interest in socializing with people of similar intellectual level; quick resolution of personal difficulties; easy boredom with routine; search for originality and authenticity; ability to redefine and extrapolate; critical spirit, ability to analyze and synthesize; desire for personal improvement, non-acceptance of imperfection at work; rejection of excessive authority; weak interest in regulations and standards; highly developed sense of humor; high-demand; persistence in satisfying your interests and issues; sensitivity to injustices, both on a personal and social level; I like research and asking many questions; restless, disruptive, annoying behavior; carelessness in writing, poor spelling; impatience with details and with learning that requires training; carelessness in completing or delivering tasks when disinterested (BRASIL, 2009, p. 19).

As is only natural, nowadays, a child who presents this condition will be referred to a psychiatrist, instead of being evaluated, didactically and pedagogically, by a team of Pedagogues, and the result is that old thing known to everyone: a label and a daily dose of medication, in order to offer you ideal conditions so that you can enjoy an authentic quality of life, socializing with your peers and carrying out tedious school tasks to your satisfaction.

THE IDEA OF EQUALITY IMPOSED ON THE BRAZILIAN EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM

The learning environment is marked by conflict and dispute. It has always been this way and the attempt to make it a place of symbolic exchanges, a euphemism for nothing being produced in terms of innovation and creativity, has caused resentment among students to such an extent that their retaliation has been the denial of manifestation. of its potential cognitive aspects, and may even suppress the manifestation of genius conditions.

In the case of gifted children, the situation gets worse, because they need a much larger space to present and test their ideas, going much further than what is commonly taught in classrooms, following the formal curriculum. Contrary to this, the proposal that was imposed on the Brazilian education system is that everyone is equal, with there being no one who knows or those who know less, they are just expressions of knowledge in different ways (Freire, 2006), a thought that does not fit with the gifted, given that their respective capacities for searching, data processing, interpretation, understanding and synthesis occur in accelerated conditions, that is, through their efforts they become more intellectually capable than their classmates.

However, subjected to a school that claims to promote inclusion, they end up trapped in learning formats that reduce them to the state of intellectual decadence to which all other students are condemned, by force of law and ideology. To get an idea of the dimension of what this straitjacket called an inclusive school represents, Iron Curtain countries that have already experienced the harmful consequences of such ideas have created special schools to receive and serve such children in their respective needs, where the curriculum is designed and designed in such a way that it allows them to develop their thoughts and experiences in accordance with their intellectual and intelligence potential, which is understood as the expression of their creativity.

The school curriculum is understood as a guide for the entire educational process, considering that it determines the path that students will take at school . It organizes the contents that will be studied, as well as the activities and skills to be developed. The problem is that, nowadays, when education becomes compulsory, that is, everyone is obliged, by force of law, to immerse themselves in school for decades on end, there was, in the same proportion, to create a mechanism in which the disinterested and the gifted felt like they were part of the machine and, as a result, those who were far above average were harmed in their natural conditions of cognitive exceptionality; one does not know what to do to take advantage of their superior talents, because throughout the initial training and throughout the continuing training process, they only seek to teach how to work with the less gifted; perhaps, because given their condition, anything they offer is seen and interpreted as *genius*; something that will not happen with geniuses, in which everything offered to them will still not be enough to satisfy their intellectual desires.

Gifted people yearn for objective and direct answers, that is, only experience can satisfy them in terms of their curiosity, and this is a condition that the contemporary school curriculum does not have the slightest concern for. This produces a student who, after a very long time at

school, does not have the minimum conditions to make a defense based on facts, only on theories and information.

THE CONTEMPORARY SCHOOL CURRICULUM AND THE DECADENCE OF HIGHER INTELLECTUAL THOUGHT

As already discussed above, gifted children need experiences that enrich them and that allow them to explore the universe of empirical knowledge, through contact with real situations and, with this, they can argue based on facts they have observed, which would lead to new forms of searches.

For this, there is a need for the curriculum to include research actions, exploring students' interests in learning about things that challenge them towards knowledge of phenomena. It is not enough to present her as a prodigy to the world, due to her ability to remember or make calculations, because this is an ability that highlights itself; It is not about your competence, which, to be exalted, would require ample spaces for work, experimentation and discussions.

As has been recommended, gifted individuals should be left to their own devices, as there are no qualified professionals to meet their demands. This is the biggest mistake imposed on someone, because it is not about teaching them techniques and processes; the didactic work is linked to guiding you, highlighting that you want to be heard, to have your ideas appreciated and judged to the point where a properly prepared tutor encourages you to experiment, produce, expose your ideas and creativity, which is your superior intelligence being put into practice.

It turns out that, nowadays, the entire learning process has been limited to the doctrine of the textbook, which has nothing of the kind, and to the *ad orechio exposition* of things that are at the level of common sense. BNCC states in every line of its pages that the authentic construction of *skills in students* must be encouraged, treating everyone as gifted and potentially brilliant; this, in theory; because, in practice, students are condemned to practice theoretical exercises without any causal link with reality, leveling everyone using the same ruler, whose name is ignorance; because there is no possibility of carrying out any type of experiment in schools, whether due to the lack of materials, the lack of qualified professionals or, even, the lack of time and financial resources.

Absent all these procedures from student life, the only solution for the teacher is to impose the truth on his authority and, with such an attitude, he condemns all students to

conventional wisdom, the one he likes, because it allows them to pass to the next series and bring them closer and closer to freedom; not scientific knowledge.

WHAT FATE IS RESERVED FOR GIFTED CHILDREN?

Gifted children are always very problematic at school, starting because, in general, they are shy individuals and feel different from others, not nurturing the same collective interests, which leads them to be harassed by their peers and this makes them even more reserved. more into their own identities.

In this case, the company and care administered by a competent guardian is of the utmost urgency, in order to balance conflict situations. However, with this model of society, which has been producing learning systems and curricula willing to make everyone equal, the fate of such children could not be any other than the common grave of collective equality that they preach so much today as a value absolute to be achieved. As a rule, if they complete their formal studies, they are marked by a deep disappointment with regular school and the entire system.

The gifted individual cannot be measured using the same ruler with which regular schools have the habit of measuring the masses that pass through their gates, for years on end. First of all, you can stand out in a certain field and not be excellent in another; sometimes even needing external help, such as reinforcement in areas of knowledge in which their less gifted colleagues excel.

From then on, it has been decided that all empirical, pedagogical and didactic support work for these students is necessary, not with the aim of fitting them into the system by *forceps* ; but, with the distinction of understanding the paths they follow so that they can achieve their goals.

THE UNIVERSALIZATION OF PUBLIC SCHOOLS FOR GIFTED CHILDREN IN THE LIGHT OF THE NATIONAL EDUCATION PLAN

The National Education Plan (PNE), approved by Law 13,005 on June 25, 2014, defines in Goal 4 as Universalization for the population aged 4 (four) to 17 (seventeen) years old with disabilities, global developmental disorders and high skills or giftedness, access to basic education and specialized educational assistance, preferably in the regular education network, with the guarantee of an inclusive educational system, multifunctional resource rooms, classes, schools or specialized services, public or affiliated (BRASIL 2014) .

In light of Law No. ^{11,494}, of June 20, 2007, strategy 4.1 of Goal 4 defines the accounting, for the purposes of the transfer of the Fund for Maintenance and Development of Basic Education and Valorization of Education Professionals - FUNDEB, enrollments of students in regular education in the public network who receive complementary and supplementary specialized educational assistance, without prejudice to the calculation of these enrollments in regular basic education, and the enrollments made, according to the most up-to-date school census, in special education offered in community institutions, confessional or philanthropic non-profit organizations, in partnership with public authorities and operating exclusively in this modality.

According to the Agência Brasil website, in Brazil, according to the 2020 School Census, there are 24,424 students with a high ability/giftedness profile enrolled in special education, but the real number could be even higher.

From the same perspective, the World Health Organization (WHO) says that 5% of the population has some type of high ability or giftedness. According to the Ministry of Education (MEC), if the more than 47 million basic education students are considered (School Census, INEP 2020), around 2.3 million students should make up this group.

The identification rate of this segment is still low in Brazil, that is, it is believed that there are many more students with high abilities or giftedness than the number generally revealed in the School Census. “This is the main challenge for the area of Special Education: identifying these students early and offering adequate care, with specialized services and resources, must be the agenda of Brazilian education institutions, once pointing out different effective methods, to define some characteristics that can point out high abilities and/or giftedness.

It is worth highlighting that the characteristics of gifted children are very different. A child's ability to learn quickly is always undeniable. They find it easier to develop a broader vocabulary and are more interested in learning, as well as in all areas of knowledge.

CONCLUSION

In this essay, we sought to highlight the incisive criticism regarding gifted children and the inability of contemporary regular schools to meet their *sui generis needs*, precisely due to the fact that, with the ideology of inclusion and universalization of learning via the education system, this deprives teachers of dedicating themselves to exploring the potential of students, having to level everyone through a castrating curriculum.

Gifted children do not find their place in the Brazilian educational system, simply because the Brazilian educational curriculum, as well as the academic training of teachers, do not have them as the target object of work. The Catholic-Christian model of learning that was imposed on Brazil tends to see those who are beyond the ordinary as aberrations of nature, who must be persecuted and conditioned to what the establishment advocates and, if they resist, they are ostracized and/or put to margin of opportunities for success.

REFERENCES

Brazil Agency. **More than 24 thousand children in Brazil are gifted.** Available at: <https://agenciabrasil.ebc.com.br/geral/noticia/2021-08/Mais-de-24-mil-criancas-no-brasil-sao-superdotadas-mostra-census#:~:text=No%20Brazil%2C%20de%20agreement%20com.de%20high%20ability%20ou%20superdota%C3%A7%C3%A3o>. Accessed on: 05 Aug. 2023.

Alencar, EMLS; Fleith, D.S. **Gifted: determinants, education and adjustment.** São Paulo: EPU, 2001.

ATTONI, Tiago; COELHO, Rebeca; MARTINS, Rafaela; LEMOS, Laura; FERNANDES, Laura; FRANCIS, Thamyris; FERNANDES, Sara; FIDELES, Karina. **Language aspects of children with high abilities/giftedness: integrative literature review.** *CEFAC Magazine*, v. 22, no. 6, p. 1-6, 2020.

BRAZIL. SEESP/MEC. **Inclusion knowledge and practices: developing skills to meet the special educational needs of students with high abilities/giftedness.** 2. Ed. Brasília: MEC, Secretariat of Special Education, 2006. (Series: Knowledge and practices of inclusion)

BRAZIL. Law n.13.005, of June 25, 2014. **Approves the National Education Plan – PNE and provides other measures.** Official Gazette of the Union, Brasília, DF., June 26, 2014. Available at: https://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/_ato2011-2014/2014/lei/l13005.htm. Accessed on: 04 Aug. 2023.

COSTA, Maira Maria da; BIANCHI, Alessandra Sant'Anna; SANTOS, Marcia Melo de Oliveira. **Characteristics of children with high abilities/Giftedness: a systematic review.** *Brazilian Journal of Special Education*, Bauru, v.28, n. 21, p. 71-88, 2022.

FREIRE, PAULO. **Pedagogy of the oppressed.** Rio de Janeiro: Peace and Land, 2006.

GARDNER, Howard. **Multiple Intelligences: Theory in Practice.** Porto Alegre: Artmed, 1995.

VYGOTSKY, LS **The social formation of the mind**. São Paulo: Martins Fontes, 2000.